

PEDIATRIC ONCOLOGY: DIFFICULTIES IN DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT

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Abstract. *This problem is not widespread enough to cause horror. However, such cases are being recorded more and more often, which causes concern. The most common reasons for the spread of cancer among children:*

- *excess solar radiation;*
- *passive smoking (early onset addiction to cigarettes);*
- *carcinogens contained in water and air masses.*
- *malnutrition that does not compensate for the deficiency of the child's body in vitamins, microelements, macroelements, amino acids;*
- *eating a lot of food that is not suitable for a child (for any normal person who cares about health, too). The list includes: smoked, fried and salted foods. Because of them, the body loses strength and cannot resist the disease;*
- *poor heredity, but here a lot depends on what age category the child falls into.*

Keywords: *children, oncology, diagnosis, treatment, prevention.*

ДЕТСКАЯ ОНКОЛОГИЯ: ТРУДНОСТИ В ДИАГНОСТИКЕ И ЛЕЧЕНИИ

Аннотация. *Эта проблема недостаточно распространена, чтобы вызывать ужас. Однако подобные случаи фиксируются все чаще и чаще, что вызывает беспокойство. Наиболее распространенные причины распространения рака среди детей:*

- *избыточная солнечная радиация;*
- *пассивное курение (раннее начало пристрастия к сигаретам);*
- *канцерогены, содержащиеся в водных и воздушных массах.*
- *неправильное питание, которое не компенсирует дефицит детского организма в витаминах, микроэлементах, макроэлементах, аминокислотах;*
- *употребление большого количества пищи, которая не подходит для ребенка (для любого нормального человека, который тоже заботится о здоровье). В список входят: копченые, жареные и соленые продукты. Из-за них организм теряет силы и не может противостоять болезни;*
- *плохая наследственность, но здесь многое зависит от того, к какой возрастной категории относится ребенок.*

Ключевые слова: *дети, онкология, диагностика, лечение, профилактика.*

There are several types of tumors:

- *embryonic: formed in the body when it is still in the embryonic state. They look like healthy cells, so it's hard to spot a problem at this stage. In this case, the child is born sick;*
- *juvenile, arising in adolescence. Reason: degeneration of mature tissues. In most cases, synovial cell carcinoma and osteogenic sarcoma are diagnosed in adolescence;*
- *neoplasms of the adult form are the most rare. But sometimes experts still make a diagnosis: nasopharyngeal carcinoma.*

If the problem was detected in time, then there is an excellent chance to save the child's life. It is important that the treatment is carried out quickly and efficiently. This will increase the chance of eliminating cancer and preventing recurrence.

Signs, oncology in children

The list of symptoms that should make parents wary includes:

- abnormally rapid weight loss, usually due to loss of appetite;
- unreasonable rise in temperature;
- changes in behavior: whims, forgetfulness, fatigue;
- increase in the size of lymph nodes;
- pallor of the skin;
- the appearance of shortness of breath;
- localized pain.

Diagnosis of pediatric oncology

It is much more difficult to detect cancer in a child than in an adult, since it may seem to parents that the baby is healthy, even if the tumor has reached the last stage of its development. Sometimes a problem is discovered quite by accident, for example, during a routine preventive study. For this reason, it is so important to remember these activities. If the attending physician suspects that the little patient is not all right, then he is obliged to send him for additional tests to find out the situation. As a rule, a biopsy puts an end to this issue. This medical term refers to a mini-surgery that involves removing a small piece of tissue from the suspicious organ and carefully examining it under a microscope. This makes it possible to determine whether there is a disease or not, what is its form and stage of development. The method that will be chosen to solve the problem depends on the results obtained. But in some cases, for example, if the organs that make up the circulatory system are in doubt, a bone marrow puncture is used.

Treatment of pediatric cancers

Doctors called pediatric oncologists and oncohematologists specialize in this. To eliminate the problem, the child is visited in special departments that are in large hospitals. Otherwise, the little patient is sent to specialized research institutes.

If we are talking about the prevention of cancer in adults, then we emphasize that in 70% of cases the lifestyle that a person leads is important. In oncology, a "risk factor" is anything that increases the likelihood of a disease. Each tumor has its own risk factors. In an adult, these are obesity, physical inactivity, overeating and an unhealthy diet, smoking and alcohol, exposure to toxic substances, and the presence of chronic diseases. However, lifestyle factors affect the body for decades before leading to disease. Children get sick too early to blame their lifestyle. It is more appropriate to analyze the lifestyle of their parents. There is an opinion that cancer prevention should begin with the planning of pregnancy. Recently, experts are inclined to believe that childhood oncology largely depends on congenital genetic defects. According to the data available today, approximately 10% of all childhood cancer patients have a genetic predisposition. But parents can reduce the harmful effects on the child's body in order to reduce the risk of DNA mutations.

The main task of oncology prevention in children is the formation of such behavioral patterns in them that will prevent the development of preventable oncological diseases in adulthood. I would like to remind you that most of our habits are formed in childhood. Studies show that if

parents lead a healthy lifestyle and eat right, children are more likely to follow their example. Never smoke. You can not smoke not only in the presence of children - tobacco toxins accumulate indoors on your clothes, increasing the risk of cancer, chronic respiratory problems. Breastfeed longer. The artificial mixture does not replace natural mother's milk with its antibodies and valuable nutrients. For the full formation of the child's immune system and cancer prevention, 9-12 months of lactation are needed.

Include greens in your children's diet. Cabbage, broccoli, watercress, spinach, parsley contain a lot of antioxidants, flavonoids and vitamins

Give the kids more fruits. The conducted studies showed that children who did not eat fruits at all, almost always suffer from one or another oncopathology in the future. The best vegetable or fruit is home grown or 100% organic, purchased from trusted growers. More Phytonutrients, Less Pesticides

Give omega-3 fatty acids. Cod liver, red fish, liquid fish oil or encapsulated forms of omega-3 acids are the key to a strong immune system for a child.

Limit salt and sugar. Eat less processed foods and canned foods - such foods usually contain excess sugar and salt. Try to cook at home with fresh ingredients.

Living near freeways, factories, and gas stations increases the chance that a child may develop blood cancer (leukemia). There has been an increase in cancer upon contact, even indirectly, with such chemical compounds and substances as benzene, cadmium, asbestos, coal, uranium, nickel, aluminum, dyes and paints, petroleum products, radon, arsenic.

Limit digital gadgets. The safety of electromagnetic radiation has not been definitively established.

Be careful with pesticides. Inside the house where children play, pesticides, herbicides and other toxic substances cannot be used and stored. Many of them can cause lymphoma, leukemia, and brain tumors.

Rid your home of toxins. Your home, especially the bedroom, kitchen and bathroom, should become an environmentally friendly area. No vinyl curtains, no Chinese plastic, no air fresheners.

Less antibiotics. Inappropriate use of antibiotics kills beneficial bacteria, undermines the immune system and predisposes to serious diseases in the future.

The ultraviolet spectrum of sunlight has already proven carcinogenic effects on body tissues, especially on the occurrence of skin cancer. Protecting yourself from direct sunlight, avoiding midday sun, staying in the shade, using sunscreen (with a sun protection spectrum of at least 50) and appropriate clothing will help you and your child avoid the risk of skin cancer.

Exercise - physical activity saturates the body with oxygen, activates metabolic processes and strengthens the immune system. It has been proven that if a child experiences sufficiently intense physical activity for an hour, at least 5 days a week, this will significantly reduce the appearance of excess body weight in him and, accordingly, the risk of developing cancer.

The sexual education of a child is the responsibility of the parents. If young people understand all the risks and use protective equipment, then, for example, ovarian or cervical cancer can be avoided;

Do not ignore vaccinations. Papillomavirus and hepatitis B virus play an important role in the development of neoplastic diseases.

Creating a harmonious atmosphere in the family will help the baby avoid stress. Its influence on the development of cancer has long been known.

It is important for parents to pay attention in time to the appearance of unusual signs and symptoms in a child:

- the presence of swelling or tumor formation;
- pallor of the skin, increased fatigue;
- unexplained bruising, pain or limping;
- prolonged fever, frequent headaches and vomiting, sudden deterioration in vision, rapid weight loss.

If you find one or more of the above symptoms in your child, do not panic, almost all of them can accompany various infectious, traumatic or autoimmune diseases. But this does not mean that when such symptoms appear, you should self-medicate. If you have any warning signs, immediately contact your pediatrician or pediatric oncologist. Remember that neoplasms in childhood are easier to treat than in adults.

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